
EVALUATION REPORT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE ZIRON PULSE NUTRITION TOOLKIT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Micronutrient deficiencies are a major public health problem affecting large parts of the world's population. Biofortification, the process of enhancing the micronutrient content in plants by plant breeding has been proven to fill the nutrient gap, especially in hard-to-reach populations. Biofortified crops are steadily being introduced, and the scale of many biofortification programs is increasing. However, there are still gaps concerning the nutrition and health benefits of biofortified beans including myths and misconceptions that hinder their utilization in the community.

The Nutrition toolkit was developed to address these nutrition and health information gaps that had been identified from a formative research that was done in Kiambu, Nyeri and Meru counties of Kenya.

The evaluation was conducted using Focus group discussions (FGD) and in-depth interviews to collect information related to knowledge, attitude, and practices on biofortified beans, and bean processing methods adopted by the communities, sources of information on biofortified beans, availability of biofortified beans, recipes tried at home, barriers to biofortified bean consumption and what consumers like most about biofortified beans. This information was gathered in order to evaluate the performance of the nutrition toolkit in terms of addressing gaps identified in formative research.

Structured interview data collection was conducted using tablet computers and open data kit (ODK) software. FGD data was recorded, transcribed, coded and summarized into themes.

Results

A total of 57 IDIs and 6 FGDs were conducted in Kiambu, Nyeri and Meru counties. Most of the respondents were female and a majority were aware of biofortified beans in the market. This information was mostly gotten from relatives/friends/neighbours, village/community meetings, and extension workers with only a small proportion indicating social media and mainstream media.

Despite the implementation of the nutrition toolkit in the three counties, health and nutrition knowledge on biofortified beans is still low with about 10% of the participants citing nutritional benefits of beans and 32% aware of the health benefits of beans. Among the health benefits mentioned are prevention of anaemia and malnutrition at 13% and 12%, respectively.

Perception towards biofortified beans was good with 50% indicating that they have less gas and 33% citing less cooking time. Advantages of biofortified beans mentioned by participants included: high yields, short growth duration, and good market price.

The participants are able to source biofortified beans mostly from the agrovet stores, from traders in the market, the shops and KALRO in that order. However, they pointed out that biofortified beans are not easily available and are expensive.

To prepare beans for consumption, participants mostly soaked the beans overnight discarded the soak water and then after cooking, they consumed the cook water which is a good practice to ensure that they get all the nutrients that may have leached.

A number of recipes have been tried by the participants with majority mentioning 3-4 recipes and the least being more than 6 recipes. This is still a limitation in bean consumption that needs more education and awareness for scaling and adoption of biofortified beans in the community. The most preferred recipes were chapati, Githeri, and mokimo. However, as much as the participants had not tried other recipes, they were all in agreement that they had everything for everyone including children, the sick and the elderly.

There were a number of methods used to reduce gas in beans including: soaking overnight, adding carrots during cooking, cooking with cabbage, cooking with garlic, and using the quick soak method.

A number of barriers were cited for bean consumption such as: difficulty in chewing, gas, not easily available expensive to procure and with about some still thinking that they are not good for health. These are myths

and misconceptions that still need more education to distill them so that consumption of biofortified bean is upscaled.

Lessons learned from Ziron pulse toolkit by participants

Despite these barriers, participants indicated that they gained new knowledge from the Ziron pulse nutrition toolkit concerning biofortified beans for example: ZIRON beans have a high yield and short maturity, the beans have wider leaves that can be used for livestock feeds and as vegetables, the added nutrients in the beans creates a sense of keenness in nutrition in the community, the beans have a higher yield, you can use the beans flour in making chapati and other recipes, the ZIRON beans have higher zinc and iron quantities than normal beans, and the benefits of iron and zinc in the body.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The Participants pointed out the high cost of the biofortified beans being a major hinderance to their consumption and adoption and hence suggested that the price should be reduction to make them accessible. Additionally, they lacked information on where to buy the beans. They also requested that they need information on different planting techniques that can be used to maximize on the yield of biofortified beans.

Study findings revealed that the selected rural communities were aware of and generally had a positive perception towards consumption, benefits and utilization of biofortified beans. The knowledge of biofortified beans was found to significantly influence their perception and utilization of biofortified beans. There was still low knowledge on the health and nutrition benefits of biofortified beans meaning that more awareness needs to be made. The number of recipes being tried were still low and more cooking demonstrations are needed. There was still lack of knowledge on where to source biofortified beans. Therefore, research institutes and relevant stakeholders should ensure that rural sensitization is promoted at a higher scale with accompanying cooking demonstration, and availing the biofortified beans to improve acceptability and utilization. There is still need for sensitization and education for the members of Nyeri County on the ZIRON-Pulse beans varieties. Consecutively, more seeds should be made available for the farmers to plant and distribute once harvested.

1.1 Introduction

The Nutrition toolkit was developed to address nutrition and health information gaps related to biofortified beans, myths, misconceptions and general lack of information faced by farmers and the general public concerning pulses. These gaps were distilled through an extensive desk review that looked into consumption and adoption of biofortified foods in Kenya and specifically the production and consumption of biofortified beans variety. A formative research also was done to gather first hand impressions of farmers, caregivers, traders and the general public in Meru, Nyeri and Kiambu counties on biofortification, nutrition knowledge about beans in general and in particular biofortification of beans with Zinc and Iron. The key issues identified include:

- Many people in the community believe that biofortified foods are Genetically Modified Foods (GMOs) or that they contain GMOs which lower immunity.
- Improved foods have led to increase in cancer cases and are they are therefore encouraged to consume traditional foods like managu instead.
- Improved beans cause acidity and gas compared to traditional ones.
- Yellow and white beans are good for diabetic and hypertensive patients

The formative research also revealed that farmers had some understanding of nutritional benefits of beans, however it was not enough to enable them make right food choices and prioritize nutrient dense foods like biofortified beans.

Against this back drop, a nutrition toolkit was developed that consisted of a nutrition resource manual for beans, fliers for farmers, caregivers, traders and the general public with information on the health and nutrition benefits of Beans. Bean Recipes were also developed and pretested in Kiambu in combination with media awareness through local FM stations, National TVs, social media and print media. Agricultural extension workers, nutritionists and community health volunteers were also trained on how to use the toolkit in the community as a reference guide to enable the them to answer nutrition and health questions related to biofortified beans.

1.2 Evaluation of the Nutrition Toolkit in Kiambu, Nyeri and Meru Counties

In-depth interviews (mothers, extension workers, farmers, traders and the general public) and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) (Farmers and Caregivers/mothers) were held in Kiambu, Meru and Nyeri counties. In each county, the participants of FGDs included farmers, mothers, and caregivers of children under 5. KII participants were made up of farmers, mothers and caregivers of children under 5, traders, the general public, and agricultural extension officers. The study was done to evaluate the performance of Ziron pulse nutrition toolkit in the three counties. Data was gathered on knowledge, attitude, and practices on biofortified beans, and bean processing methods adopted by the communities, sources of information on biofortified beans, availability of biofortified beans, recipes tried at home, barriers to biofortified bean consumption and what consumers like most about biofortified beans. This information was gathered in order to evaluate the performance of the nutrition toolkit in terms of addressing gaps identified in formative research.

1.3 Description of the Study Areas

1.3.1 Kiambu County

Tigoni ward is located in the Limuru sub-county, while Karuri ward is located in the Kiambaa sub-county, all of which are in Kiambu County. Kiambu County is located within Nairobi Metropolitan Region. Its capital is Kiambu and its largest town is Thika. The county has a population of 2, 417, 735 with 40% rural and 60% urban. Agriculture is the leading economic activity in Kiambu County as the soil fertility is conducive for livestock keeping and the production of various crops. The major crops grown in the county include maize, beans, Irish potatoes, and cabbages. Agriculture contributes to about 17% of the population's income. Its proximity to Nairobi, the capital city of Kenya, also makes it a potential fresh food basket for the urbanities.

1.3.2 Nyeri County

Kieni East is a sub-county in Nyeri County that has a total population of 110,376 people, and a population density of 246 per km² according to the recently carried out 2019 population census. It has four wards namely Naromoru/Kiamathaga ward, Gakawa ward, Thegu River ward and Kabaruru ward. Kieni East sub-county is located on the leeward side of Mt. Kenya, making some parts of it dry as it features semi-arid areas.

However, despite being a semi-arid area, it is without a doubt one of the food baskets for Nyeri County as it has good soils and a favorable topography. Most of the crops grown include Irish potatoes, maize, beans, cabbages as well as rearing of livestock. With the agricultural sector being the mainstay of the economy of Nyeri County, the County Government of Nyeri has endeavored to focus on increasing water supply in the region. As such, the county government has drilled several boreholes in the sub-county so that farming is sustained. With the increased water supply in Kieni East, there has been a boost in food production not only for the county but also for the country as well.

1.3.3 Meru County

Tigania Central is a sub-county in Meru County which is located around the highland regions of Mt. Kenya. Meru is the leading county in horticulture production in Kenya. Agriculture is the major economic activity in this county due to its rich volcanic soils in the high-altitude areas. Coffee, tea, French beans and dairy products are Meru's primary produce. Wholesale and retail trade also play important roles in the county's economy.

2.1 Methodology

Pretesting of the tools was initially done in Kiambu county involving 1FGD and 5 in depth interviews. The FGDs participants were 13 farmers, while in depth interview participants were 5 mothers and caregivers of children under 5. After the pretest, the study was conducted in Kiambu, Nyeri and Meru counties using FGDs and in-depth interviews as shown on table 1. Semi-structured questionnaires were used to administer FGDs comprising open-ended questions. The in-depth interview questionnaire was digitized using KOBO, and the feedback was fed to the KOBO collect software. Data analysis was done using Microsoft Excel.

Table 1. Participant Distributions for IDIs and FGDs in Kiambu, Nyeri, and Meru counties

Respondent Category	Kiambu	Nyeri	Meru	Total
In-depth interviews (IDIs)				
Mothers	5	5	5	15
Farmers	5	5	5	15
Traders	2	2	2	6
General Public	5	5	5	15
Extension Workers	2	2	2	6
Total IDIs				57
Focus Group Discussions (10 per Group)				
Farmers	1	1	1	3
Mothers/ Caregivers	1	1	1	3
Total FGDs				6

3.0 Key findings

3.1 Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Results (figure 1) indicates that majority of the respondents in each county were females.

Figure 1: Gender of the respondents

3.2 Awareness of biofortified beans

Study findings (figure 2) reveal that majority of the respondents in each county were aware of biofortified beans. However, in Meru County a considerable number of respondents (41%) were not aware of biofortified beans. This may be because cooking demonstrations and awareness campaigns were not sufficiently done in this county.

Figure 2: Number of people aware of biofortified beans

3.3. Source of information on biofortified beans

The key source of information on biofortified beans are shown on figure 3. Information was received from health extension workers, relatives/friends/neighbors and in village/ community meetings. In Nyeri county, information was sourced from relatives/friends and neighbors (47%). While in Meru County, this was mainly from extension workers (40%), and village/community meetings (40%). Similarly, in Kiambu County extension workers (32%) provided most of the information including village/community meetings (32%). Other sources of information reported by respondents in Kiambu and Nyeri Counties included radio, and social media. The fact that the majority of the respondents were aware of biofortified beans is an indication that biofortified beans are gaining recognition.

Figure 3: Source of awareness of biofortified beans

3.4. Knowledge of nutrients found in Biofortified beans

Results in figure 4 indicate that respondents from all the three counties correctly identified nutrients found in biofortified beans, however, the proportion was small compared to the general population studied. Participants identified nutrients such as iron, zinc, proteins and fiber. However, respondents from Kiambu County were unable to identify protein, while those from Meru County did not identify fiber as nutrient contained in biofortified beans.

Figure 4: Knowledge of nutrients found in biofortified beans

3.5. Knowledge on health benefits of biofortified beans

Majority of the respondents from all the three counties correctly identified that biofortified beans are good for health (Meru 32%, Kiambu 28%, and Nyeri 22%) and are good for iron status (Nyeri 20%, Kiambu 15%, and Meru 13%) as shown on figure 5. Other correct responses reported include biofortified beans are good for brain development, boost immunity and repair worn out tissues.

Figure 5: Knowledge of benefits of eating biofortified beans.

3.6. Knowledge of health problems prevented by consuming biofortified beans

Study results (Figure 6) shows that some of the respondents from all the three counties were knowledgeable on the health problems prevented by consuming biofortified beans as indicated in figure 6. Respondents from Meru County identified Anemia (13%) as the major disease prevented by consuming biofortified beans. Other diseases listed from Meru County include HIV, erectile dysfunction, and diarrhea. In Nyeri County, majority of the respondents listed malnutrition (12%) and others listed Anemia (6%), and diarrhea (2%). In Kiambu County, majority of the participants identified malnutrition (8%). Other diseases listed in Kiambu County include erectile dysfunction (3%) and diarrhea (2%).

Figure 6: Knowledge of health problems prevented by consuming biofortified beans

The preponderance of average and good knowledge of biofortified beans in this study highlights that effective sensitization of consumers on biofortified is ongoing in remote areas as shown in the involvement of health extension officers in the dissemination of information. However, efforts should be intensified so that outcomes can increase.

3.7. Perception towards consumption of biofortified beans

Study results (Figure 7) showed that majority of the respondents from all the three counties had a positive perception towards the consumption of biofortified beans. This is reflected in the opinion of majority of respondents that biofortified beans give less gas (Kiambu 50%, Meru 40% and Nyeri 30%) and have a good taste (Kiambu 33%, Nyeri 33%, and Meru 27%). Some respondents from Nyeri (33%) and Meru (19%) opined that biofortified beans take a short time to cook. A few other respondents (Kiambu 6%, Meru 2%) also suggested that biofortified beans cause no allergic reactions.

Figure 7: Perception towards biofortified beans consumption

3.8. Advantages of biofortified beans

In comparison to other non-biofortified beans, as shown in figure 8, overall results showed that majority of the respondents had a positive perception towards utilization of biofortified beans. The study assessed bean utilization by inquiring amount of yield obtained from produce, duration of growth, cost of seeds, and physical characteristics of the biofortified beans. Majority of the respondents from all the three counties dubbed biofortified beans to have higher yield (Nyeri 44%, Meru 42% and Kiambu 12%) and took a short time to grow (Meru 37%, Nyeri 35%, and Kiambu 24%). Some respondents from Kiambu county dubbed biofortified beans cheaper (24%), had desirable physical characteristics (12%), storage superiorisity (12%), and higher nutritional benefits (12%). A few respondents from Nyeri County also dubbed biofortified beans to have desirable physical characteristics (13%), and are resistant to pest (8%).

Figure 8: Advantages of biofortified beans

3.9 Source of biofortified beans

Study findings as indicated in figure 9 showed that the majority of the respondents purchased biofortified beans from agro vet stores (Kiambu 69%, Nyeri 25%, and Meru 14%), KARLO (Meru 29%, Nyeri 25% and Kiambu 15%), and shops (Meru 29%, Nyeri 17%, and Kiambu 15%). The high number of participants purchasing from agro vet stores and KARLO could be attributed to information dissemination from health extension officers from the ministry of agriculture. Some participants from Meru and Nyeri (29%; 8%) counties reported to also purchase biofortified beans from other farmers. Upon interviewing traders, they reported to mostly sell beans that are either high in iron and normal beans. Units used to sell beans are either in kilograms, cans or bags. This could be explain why some of the respondents in Nyeri and Kiambu (25%; 23%) purchase in market/street strand.

Figure 9: Source of purchase of biofortified beans

3.10 Bean preparation methods

Bean preparation methods describes activities done before cooking beans into desired recipes. The study investigated how respondents prepared their beans by inquiring whether they soaked beans prior to cooking, replaced soaking water and consumed cooking water. Results from Figure 10 indicate that majority of respondents from Kiambu and Nyeri Counties reported to soak beans before cooking, while majority of respondents from Meru County did not soak their beans before cooking. With regards to replacing soaking water, majority of the respondents from all the three counties reported to replace soaking water. With reference to consuming cooking water, majority of respondents from Meru and Nyeri Counties reported to consume cooking water, while majority of respondents from Kiambu County reported to not consuming cooking water.

Figure 10: Bean preparation methods

"I first boil the beans and cook them then mash them then add wheat flour. I like it in that, because I know I'm still eating protein and then when mixed with carbohydrates, it gives me more strength. When I do that, I reduce the amount of flour I use, because even the flour is expensive."- Mother/ Caregiver, Nyeri County.

3.11 Bean Recipes tried

Figure 11: No of people who have tried bean recipes/ how many recipes they have tried

The study results represented in Figure 11, showed that majority of the respondents from all the three counties had tried the bean recipes. With reference to the number of bean recipes tried, the study noted that majority of the respondents from all the three counties tried between 3 to 4 bean recipes (Nyeri 82%, Meru 82%, and Kiambu 40%). Some respondents (Kiambu 30%, Nyeri 6%, and Kiambu 6%) reported to have tried at least one to two bean recipes while others tried more than 6 bean recipes (Nyeri 10%, Meru 10%, and Kiambu 10%).

3.12 Commonly prepared bean recipes

In Meru, the most commonly prepared bean recipe reported was bean stew, followed by mukimo and githeri, others mentioned were; bean porridge and rice mixed with beans as shown in Figure 12. In Kiambu County, the most preferred bean recipes as shown in figure 8 include chapatti (12%) and cakes (12%). Some respondents reported preferring bean stew (8%), mandazi (8%), mashed beans and potatoes (8%), Mukimo (8%), samosas (8%), githeri (8%), porridge (8%), and mushenye (8%). Other recipes listed include kebab, cookies, and pancakes. The preferred bean recipes could explain why majority of the respondents listed githeri (22%), chapatti (22%), mandazi (11%), cake (11%) and bean stew (11%) as the bean recipes tried at home as shown in figure 13.

Figure 12: Common Bean Recipes (Meru County)

Mukimo. We boil beans then, later add the bananas, potatoes and vegetables and mash them.-respondent in, Tigania Central, Meru

Figure 13: Most preferred bean recipes and bean recipes tried at home (Kiambu County)

Mukimo as it's very sweet and ones its cooked together with cabbage, it can be eaten twice, basically saying that it last longer while still maintaining its freshness

(Mother, Karuri ward, Kiambu County)

Githeri as it is rich in fiber that aids in constipation. It's also economical, as it can be eaten both as lunch and dinner

(Caregiver of children under 5, Karuri, Kiambu Ward)

3.13 Factors that influence biofortified bean utilization

Results (Figure 14) revealed that majority of respondents associated biofortified bean utilization to the awareness of the variety of bean soaking methods which was linked to the reduction of GIT disturbance. The different beans soaking methods vary in the amount of time required for adequate soaking. The Traditional soak involves soaking the beans for a prolonged period of time, 8 hours to overnight, thereafter, discarding the soak water, rinsing then boiling the beans with fresh water. Quick soak which is the fastest method to soak beans involves boiling beans for some minutes, then draining the water and continuing the boiling with fresh water. Half of the participants in Meru County reported using the Traditional soak method while the other half use the Quick soak method when preparing their beans. In Kiambu County the most used soaking method listed were soaking overnight (38%), and addition of carrots (31%). Some (19%) respondents also reported to use quick soak method. The study also noted that other methods employed to reduce gas include cooking with cabbage (19%), and garlic (6%).

Figure 14: Bean soaking methods used to reduce GIT disturbance (Kiambu County)

Sometimes I soak them or when I am in a hurry I place them in a jiko to boil then, when it's almost cooked I pour the water, add some fresh water and boil again.

(Farmer, Tigania Central, Meru)

Inclusivity of the Recipes

Biofortified bean utilization could also be associated with the fact that majority of respondents felt that the bean recipes had something for everyone, including children, men and the elderly. Almost all the participants in Meru County agreed that the bean recipes have something for everyone regardless of age group. In Kiambu County some respondents associated biofortified bean utilization to the fact that it is safe for consumption for people with dietary restrictions as indicated below. People with knowledge of the benefits of interventions are likely to adopt practices that are promoted to prevent consequences of not doing so, and thus knowledge of biofortified beans will influence household purchase and utilization frequency.

...yes. For example children like when it's cooked with mashed potatoes or arrowroots. They also like rice with bean stew, chapatti, and cake.

(Mother, Karuri ward, Kiambu County)

...elderly can also consume foods such as porridge, ugali and chapatti and mukimo

(Farmer, Tigoni ward, Kiambu County)

Very few participants in Meru County, however, stated that the bean recipes are mainly suitable for children and young people who don't have many stomach problems but as people age, they develop many stomach issues. You know, children don't have many stomach problems they eat everything, but as you grow, things change and gas starts being an issue.

(Farmer, Tigania Central, Meru)

3.14 Barriers to consumption and utilization of biofortified beans

Barriers to trying various Bean recipes

In Meru County the respondents were asked which bean recipes they dislike most, Githeri was the most disliked dish followed by beans stew, the reasons for disliking these recipes are shown in the table 6 below. A few (n=6) respondents in Kiambu County mentioned trying samosas (50%), kebab (33%), and mandazi (17) as shown in figure 15. The main reason for not trying the named recipes was the amount of work that goes into preparation of the recipes and unpleasant samosas taste as indicated below. The amount of time taken to prepare the named recipes could be associated with the fact that farmers, mothers and caregivers of children under 5 have busy schedules and lack adequate time to prepare the complicated recipes. Therefore, more emphasize should be made on the varied bean recipes require shorter time to prepare. Recipes that take time but are still sweet could be encouraged to be prepared on special occasions.

Table 2 :Most Disliked Bean Recipes and Reasons for Dislike(Meru County)

Bean recipe	Reason for dislike
<i>Githeri</i>	It's difficult for children to chew or swallow hence they don't get full
Beans stew	It contains more gas than the other bean recipes

Figure 15: Most disliked recipes (Kiambu County)

"...samosa- its good but takes a lot of time to prepare. The preparation process is tedious"

(Farmer, Tigoni ward, Kiambu County)

...Improve the beans added to the samosa recipe, as children did not like. Maybe it could be mashed and added other things to make it tastier...

(Mother, Karuri ward, Kiambu County)

Barriers to bean utilization

Majority of the respondents from all the three counties reported that the lack of biofortified beans (Meru 67%, Nyeri 55%, and Kiambu 40%) is largest barrier against utilization of biofortified beans as indicated in figure 16. Some respondents also disagreed to the assertions that biofortified beans are cheaper (Nyeri 27%, Meru, 11% and Kiambu 11%) and that are not good for health (Kiambu 27%). Other barriers listed include long cooking time, and poor yield. This could be attributed to the slight difference in the characteristics of the population, as it is expected farmers may have a better understanding and healthy perception of biofortified beans than consumers, as they are the first point of contact with the agricultural extension officers. Therefore, relevant stakeholders should ensure that these biofortified beans are made available and affordable in local markets.

Figure 16: Barriers to bean utilization

3.15 New information Learned by Respondents

The new information gathered by the respondents include the following:

- ZIRON beans have a high yield and short maturity.
- The beans have wider leaves that can be used for livestock feeds and as vegetables.
- The added nutrients in the beans creates a sense of keenness in nutrition in the community.
- The beans have a higher yield.
- You can use the beans flour in making chapatti.
- The ZIRON beans have higher zinc and iron quantities than other beans.
- The benefits of zinc in the body.

4.0 Recommendations to improve biofortified beans consumption and utilization

In Nyeri County, the ways to improve the bean recipes as suggested by the respondents included adding vegetables like zucchini, coriander, and onions as well as spices like garlic, ginger and curry powder to improve on the taste and colour of the beans as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Ways of improving bean consumption and utilization

In Kiambu County, study results noted that participants suggested addition of spices to improve the bean recipes as indicated below. Some of the spices listed include ginger, garlic, royco, onions and curry powder.

When cooking bean stew, one can add you can add ginger and garlic to add some taste to it so that you can have the appetite to eat more. For those who love royco, you can add a cube. But if you just cook with onions without making any additions, it becomes flat. It has no taste.

(Mother, Karuri ward, Kiambu County)

...curry powder could be added to some of the bean recipes, like samosa...

(Farmer, Tigoni ward, Kiambu Ward)

In Meru County, the participants were asked if they know of ways of improving the bean recipes, listed below are the responses that they gave:

- Adding carrots to the beans enhances the taste
- Adding green vegetables improve the taste
- Adding spices such as courgette, capsicum and coriander
- Adding potatoes or arrow roots to the beans
- Mixing the bean recipes with cabbage
- Mixing beans with cooked bananas make it sweet
- Frying the beans is better than the other cooking methods
- Increasing the ratio of beans to maize in githeri makes it mashy

The most common responses mentioned in improving the bean recipes were; adding carrots, green vegetables and spices to the beans.

Mix the githeri with cooked bananas, potatoes and greens. Children can even have this.

(Mother, Tigania Central, Meru).

"I'm recommending that people should keep on being educated, so that they know about it the government can send people from place to place so they know the benefits of this one. I also wasn't eating beans but I can eat these ones, even my family loves it the village people had bought from me, but I just measure just a kilo so that they could all get it and know the benefits. If you go on teaching people, they will understand the advantages of these beans and how it helps someone in the body."- mother/caregiver, Nyeri County.

Other recommendations the study noted would improve utilization of biofortified beans include the following:

- Reduction of bean prices
- Information of where to purchase the beans
- Different planting techniques that can be used to maximize on the yield of biofortified beans

5.0 Conclusion

Study findings revealed an average level of biofortified beans in selected rural communities of Kiambu, Meru, and Nyeri County. The respondents had a positive perception towards consumption, benefits and utilization of biofortified beans. The knowledge of biofortified beans was found to significantly influence their perception and utilization of biofortified beans. Therefore, research institutes and relevant stakeholders should ensure that rural sensitization is promoted at a higher scale with accompanying cooking demonstration, and availing the biofortified beans to improve acceptability and utilization. there is still need for sensitization and education for the members of Nyeri County on the ZIRON-Pulse beans varieties. Consecutively, more seeds should be made available for the farmers to plant and distribute once harvested.

Appendices: Images

Image 1: ongoing in-depth interview with a Crops Extension Officer in Nyeri County.

Image 2: FGD with farmers in Nyeri County.

Image 3: Mothers/Caregivers FGD in the Ministry of Agriculture Sub-county offices in Meru, Tigania Central, Mikinduri Ward.

Image 4: Farmers FGD in the Ministry of Agriculture Sub-county offices in Meru, Tigania Central, Mikinduri Ward.

Image 5: In-depth Interview with a member of Public in Meru, Tigania Central, Mikinduri Ward.

